

COMPARISON OF COWPEA (*VIGNA UNGUICULATA*) STORAGE CHARACTERISTICS UNDER DIFFERENT STORAGE MEDIA AND CONDITIONS

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Abstract

This research was carried out to compare cowpea storage characteristics using different storage medium, under different weather conditions. Several technologies reputedly attribute losses of stored cowpea grain to *bruchid* beetles. Comparison of these different postharvest storage methods can provide the basis for deciding which performs best in terms of weight loss, pest infestation and nutritive losses. Proximate analysis was carried out before, during and after storage with two month intervals, over four months of storage in three storage media: a seed gene bank, modified anthill rhombus, and a covered container (the control). Temperature, humidity, and weight values (for moisture content analysis) were taken during the storage period. Results showed that the cowpea seed sample, stored in the AC section of the seed gene bank, proved to be more tolerant to pest infestation compared to seed samples, stored in the Modified anthill rhombus, and seed samples, stored under ambient conditions. The cowpea seeds weight recorded reduction after infestation, which also was significant when compared to the non-infested seeds in the seed gene bank. Proximate analysis of cowpea seeds after infestation showed a decrease in the value of carbohydrate content and protein, while crude fibre, moisture, fat and total ash recorded increased. Further research should be carried out on cowpea storage

under different weather conditions, with and without insecticide, and using more media such as jute bags, etc. There should also be an extension of the storage period more than the four months.

Keywords: cowpea storage, pest infestation, proximate analysis, seed gene bank.

DOI: 10.21303/2504-5695.2022.002313

1. Introduction

Cowpea, *Vigna unguiculata* (L) Walp, is an indigenous African annual legume crop, which is also called Southern pea, Black eye pea, etc. It is an important leguminous crop, largely grown by smallholder farmers in sub-Saharan Africa for food security and animal feed [1]. Cowpea is the most economically important indigenous African legume crop [2]. Africa accounts for about 75 % of the world's cowpea production, with Nigeria and Niger dominating. Although indigenous to Southeast Africa, cowpea has spread worldwide and it is extensively cultivated and consumed in regions of Asia, South and Central America, the Caribbean, the United States, the Middle East and Southern Europe [3]. Cowpea can be stored for a short term at around 12 % moisture content or less, with 8 to 9 % recommended for long term storage [4].

Cowpea is grown and consumed for its high protein (23–25 %) and carbohydrate (57 %) content, while the leaves are also high in protein (between 27 and 34 %). It is also capable of providing solution to the protein-carbohydrate imbalance in most Nigerians' nutrition [5]. Cowpea has a high nutrient content and high values for dry seed protein content (25 %), which makes it highly digestible compared to other legumes [6]. Unlike other leguminous grains, such as soya beans and groundnuts, which are oil-protein seeds, cowpea grains are starch-protein seeds and offer a wider pattern of utilization than any other legume in Africa [7]. Cowpea is cultivated for its leaves, green pods, grain and haulm for livestock feed. It is a major source of plant protein. It contains minerals (such as Calcium and Iron) and amino acids (including lysine, tryptophan and methionine), which improve human nutrition and health status [8].

Grain cereals are the food security staples of the poor masses around the globe. However, a significant proportion of these crops, especially cowpea are lost during storage. Cowpea farmers in the West Africa lose a significant portion of their crop during storage due to insects (cowpea weevil) [9]. The main purpose of storage is to even out fluctuations in market supply by taking the produce off the market in surplus seasons, and releasing it back into the market in lean seasons. Cowpea storage techniques have always battled with eradicating insect pests, while maintaining the nutritional quality of the grains. Storage structures available to local cowpea farmers are mostly inadequate, inefficient and unable to adequately provide the needed environment for successful storage. However, if these grains are stored without good storage techniques, insect pests pose a significant threat to the shelf life of the stored grains. These insects reproduce rapidly, thus a few of the insects within a collection of cowpeas can cause significant damage within a short period of time.

This necessitates modified, indigenous based structures, which can be used by local farmers for storing grain crops without the attendant problems, associated with their storage, and which can compare favorably with other modern methods. Hence, there is a need to ascertain viable methods of storing cowpea, while maintaining the nutritional and seed quality.

The main objective of this work was to assess the storage characteristics of cowpea under different storage conditions and storage media.

2. Materials and Methods

The project was carried out in two locations:

1) the Crop Production Technology Department of the Federal College of Forestry (Jericho Ibadan, Nigeria), which lies between latitude 7°23' N and longitude 3°15' E, dominated by a rainfall pattern from 1400–1500 mm, average temperature of 32 °C and average humidity values of 80–85 % with two distinct seasons of wet (April–October) and dry (November–March) [10];

2) the National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRAB), which is located in Moor Plantation, Ibadan (Nigeria) on the latitude 7°22' N of the equator and longitude 3°55' E of the Greenwich Meridian. The climate is characterized by high temperatures and a bimodal rainfall pattern. The annual and total mean rainfall is 1,435.8 and 99.87 mm respectively [11].

The following steps were carried out in the course of the work:

1. *Cowpea procurement.* Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L, Walp) was bought from the local market at Bodija, Ibadan North, Oyo State (Nigeria).

2. *Cowpea storage.* Cowpea was stored under the following conditions for four months:

– in a modified anthill rhombus [12];

– under controlled temperature and humidity (in the seed gene bank) at the National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRAB), situated at Moor Plantation, Ibadan, Nigeria;

– under ambient climatic conditions (The Control) at the National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology NACGRAB, situated at Moor Plantation, Ibadan.

3. *Measurement of cowpea storage characteristics.* The following storage characteristics were assessed during the course of the work:

– temperature: Temperature values were taken with the aid of a thermometer three times daily (at 7 am, 1 pm, and 7 pm). Average weekly values were computed from the results;

– humidity: Humidity values were taken with the use of a hygrometer, three times daily (at 7 am, 1 pm, and 7 pm). Average values were computed from the results with the use of the relative humidity table;

– moisture content: Grain moisture content was also calculated by taking the 100-seed weight of cowpea stored weekly.

4. *Nutritive analysis.* Proximate analysis was carried out before, during (half way through storage, at the 2-month mark) and after storage of cowpea under each storage media.

5. *Physical characteristics.* The stored cowpea was assessed for rodents, insect infestation and mold growth every week. This was noted using a 5 point Likert scale, where:

– 1 – No pest infestation or mold;

– 2 – Low pest infestation and slight mold;

– 3 – Average pest infestation and mold;

– 4 – High pest infestation and mold;

– 5 – Very high pest infestation and mold [13].

3. Results and Discussions

Table 1 shows the mean temperatures, measured across all storage structures over 18 weeks. The highest mean temperature was recorded under ambient conditions (CONTROL) with the value of 31 °C in weeks 2 and 7. The least mean temperature was recorded in cowpea, stored in the seed gene bank (AC) with the value of 22.1 °C in week 4. Cowpea, stored in the seed gene bank (AC), showed consistently lower mean temperatures across all weeks, followed by those, stored in the Modified Anthill Rhombus (MAR), with cowpea, stored under ambient conditions showing the highest mean values across all the weeks.

Cowpea, stored in the modified anthill, rhombus had the highest mean relative humidity values across all the weeks with the highest reading of 85 %, seen in week 2 (**Table 2**). Cowpea, stored under ambient conditions and in the seed gene bank, had similar humidity readings, with seed gene bank readings being slightly higher than control values in weeks 3, 5, 6 and 8.

Initial proximate cowpea values showed Moisture content as 4.65 %, Lipid 1.85 %, Ash 5.34 %, Crude fibre 9.23 %, Protein 25.65 %, Carbohydrate 53.78 % (**Table 3**).

During storage, proximate results show that the black eyed cowpea sample, stored under ambient conditions, had the lowest moisture content and the sample, stored under AC, had the highest moisture content with the value 3.77 and 4.35 % respectively. The result shows that the black eyed cowpea sample, stored under AC and MAR, had the highest lipid with the value of 3.32

and 3.32 % respectively, while the sample, stored under CONTROL, had the lowest lipid with the value 2.69 %.

Table 1

Mean weekly temperature of the stored cowpea (°C)

Weeks	Samples		
	MAR	AC	CONTROL
1	26.5	23.2	31
2	28	22.3	29
3	26	25.4	29.5
4	27.5	22.1	25
5	25.5	25.4	29.5
6	26.5	24.8	28
7	29	25.2	28.5
8	28.5	25.8	30.5
9	25.2	24.3	25.6
10	24.2	25.2	26.7
11	26.1	22.5	28
12	25.1	23.6	27.6
13	26.6	21.6	27
14	25.6	24.5	27.5
15	26.5	23.7	28
16	26	23.9	27
17	25.7	24.5	27.6
18	27.5	25.5	28

Table 2

Mean weekly relative humidity of the stored cowpea (%)

Weeks	Samples		
	MAR	AC	CONTROL
1	65	31	37
2	85	30	39
3	78	32	38
4	70	27	31
5	62	32	38
6	65	31	37
7	79	32	38
8	75	33	39
9	78	30	36
10	76	29	35
11	75	31	38
12	72	28	32
13	75	30	37
14	76	32	39
15	78	29	36
16	78	28	35
17	82	32	39
18	79	30	35

Also, the result shows that the sample, stored under AC, had the highest ASH with the value of 5.55 %, while the sample, stored under MAR, had the lowest ASH with the value of 3.86 %. The sample, stored under ambient conditions, had the highest crude fibre with the value of 8.24 %, while the sample, stored under AC, in the seed gene bank, had the lowest value of 7.53 %.

Table 3

Proximate analysis results of cowpea seeds before, during and after storage

Sample	Moisture	Lipid	Ash	Crude fibre	Protein	C.H.O
Before storage	4.65	1.85	5.34	9.23	25.65	53.78
During storage						
CONTROL	3.77	2.69	5.44	9.24	25.98	53.27
AC	4.35	3.32	5.55	9.53	26.24	53.02
MAR	3.9	3.32	5.86	9.58	25.7	53.06
After storage						
CONTROL	3.6	2.85	5.9	9.46	26.71	53.23
AC	3.95	3.5	5.24	9.21	26.65	52.85
MAR	3.2	3.65	5.56	9.32	26.85	53.25

Note: MAR – Modified Anthill Rhombus; AC – Air conditioned seed gene bank; C.H.O – Carbohydrate

The protein value of the sample, stored under AC, is 26.24 %, which is the highest value, and the lowest value is 25.7 % of the sample, stored under MAR.

The result also shows that the sample, stored under MAR, had the highest CHO value of 53.25 %, while the sample, stored under AC, had the lowest value of 52.85 %.

The initial moisture content value was taken during the first month of storage and the final moisture content value was taken after four months of storage (Table 4). The sample, stored in the MAR, had the lowest moisture content with the value of 7.52 %, while the sample, stored in the ambient condition, had the highest moisture content with the value of 9.00 %.

Table 4

Moisture content of stored cowpea

Sample	Initial weight, kg	Final weight, kg	Moisture content, %
MAR	0.5095	0.5056	0.8
SGB	0.5095	0.5087	0.16
CONTROL	0.5095	0.5064	0.61

Fig. 1 shows the 5 point Likert scale, where:

- 1 – No pest infestation or mold;
- 2 – Low pest infestation and slight mold;
- 3 – Average pest infestation and mold;
- 4 – High pest infestation and mold;
- 5 – Very high pest infestation and mold [13].

Fig. 1. Pest infestation and mold levels of stored cowpea

From weeks 1–6, there was no pest infestation, and the seed of the sample was not moldy. There was slight infestation of pest and moldiness of seed from weeks 6–16 in the seed sample, stored under ambient conditions. From weeks 18–20, there was an average infestation of pest and moldiness of seed, stored under RHOMBUS and the CONTROL. There was no pest infestation and moldiness in the seed sample, stored in the AC throughout the period of storage.

This study shows that the cowpea seed sample, stored in the AC section of the seed gene bank, proved to be more tolerant to pest infestation compared to seed samples, stored in the Modified anthill rhombus and seed samples under ambient conditions. The cowpea seeds weight recorded reduction after infestation, which also was significant when compared to the non-infested seeds in the seed gene bank. The proximate analysis of cowpea seeds after infestation showed a decrease in the value of carbohydrate content and protein, while crude fibre, moisture, fat and total ash recorded increased.

Study limitations included inability to store cowpea in long term freezer storage, under various weather conditions (rainy, and dry season/harmattan), and using pesticide/not to further assess the storage characteristics under such conditions. It should be noted, that received findings are solely limited to cowpea storage in a modified anthill rhombus, under A.C., and ambient conditions in South West Nigeria, during dry season. Further studies can explore cowpea storage characteristics under different weather conditions, in other parts of the country, and under other indigenous storage media, such as evaporative coolers.

This study compared cowpea storage characteristics under different storage media. Further research should be carried out on cowpea storage under different weather conditions, with and without insecticide, and using more media such as jute bags, etc. There should also be an extension of the storage period more than the four months.

4. Conclusions

In the course of the research, we have shown that cowpea showed promising results in terms of pest infestation (none until week 18), moisture content (7.52 %) and nutritional quality when stored in a modified anthill rhombus. While cowpea performed better under AC storage, the modified rhombus came in as a close second. More work can be done to further improve the storage characteristics of such indigenous structures to help farmers who may not be able to afford more expensive storage systems, such as Ac or freezer storage.

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Received date 15.12.2021

Accepted date 21.01.2022

Published date 31.01.2022

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How to cite: Olunloyo, O., Olunloyo, A., Ibiyeye, D., Akala, A., Ajiboye, O., Afeye, F., Taiye, A. R., Adegoke, F. M., Oladipupo, B. (2022). Comparison of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) storage characteristics under different storage media and conditions. EUREKA: Life Sciences, 1, 11–17. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21303/2504-5695.2022.002313>